

A Historical Analysis of Nigeria’s Judicial Approaches to the Application of International Law in Post-Independence Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper examined Nigeria’s application of international law in her legal system especially in the post-independence period. As a signatory to most international agreements, the study discussed the extent to which Nigeria has complied with international law provisions and the implication for human rights, environmental protection and economic development. Utilising both primary and secondary sources of data, the study employed a narrative, descriptive and analytical historical approach, incorporating archival materials to substantiate empirical findings. These sources were subjected to textual and contextual analysis to ascertain their accuracy. The study found a significant difference between established international legal practices and their application in Nigeria during administrations under civilian rule and the military. It also identified other barriers to the effective implementation of international law within the Nigerian legal system. These challenges have substantially hindered the alignment of domestic laws with international obligations and this has in turn, impacted on the Nigerian legal landscape. The study stressed therefore, the need to integrate international treaties into country’s domestic legal framework and in its conclusion called for comprehensive reforms to address the impediments whilst advocating an interplay between domestic and international law to promote a robust legal system in Nigeria.

Keywords: Nigeria, Judicial Approach, International Law and Post-Independence

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1. Introduction

The role of International Law in the domestic legal practices of Nigeria, especially in the post-colonial period is intrinsic. By definition, International Law refers to the universal system of rules and principles concerning the relations between sovereign states, and relations between states and international organisations. It includes the general rules and principles that are applicable in dealing with the conduct of the state in

the international community.¹ Sovereign states could ratify agreements under various bodies or organisations, to regulate the behaviours and development of the different sectors of endeavours. This could be in the form of treaties or conventions which are expected to apply to member states within the global community.² Nigeria, like several other countries of the world, is a signatory to several treaties and conventions that make up part of her laws. Once in force, treaties are binding on the parties and become part of international law.³ Section 12 of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (as amended) provides that, no treaty shall have force of law in Nigeria except to the extent to which such a treaty has been enacted into law by the National Assembly.⁴ This means for any international law to be effective and have the force of legal enforcement in Nigeria, it must have been domesticated through the National Assembly of Nigeria. This is a classic demonstration of dualist legal traditions which professes that national and international law operate separately.⁵

However, many of the treaties signed by Nigeria have been embedded in the constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria as justiciable, while others regarded as non-justiciable have been enacted into laws by the National Assembly.

2. Historical Evolution of Nigeria's Legal System

The annexation of Lagos marked the beginning of the introduction of British legal principles into Nigeria. The invasion was occasioned by colonial quest of the British to occupy the present-day Nigeria for imperialist expansion. The new imperialist administration required a robust legal system, hence the introduction of English law into Lagos in 1863; a law that eventually spread across the whole of Nigeria.⁶ Upon annexation, British common law was initially applied to European settlers in Nigeria, before the indigenes. This was a legal imposition on the pretext of “civilising” the people of the colonies.⁷ The introduction of British law into Lagos paved the way for its replication in other parts of Nigeria as it extended its influence over the lands.

3. Customary Law in Nigeria before Colonialism

Before British colonial rule, Nigeria was a multicultural entity with different ethnic groups having their own peculiar system of government and laws. These systems were mainly founded on the customs and traditions of the people, hence the name “customary law.” Customary law emanates from the traditional usage and practice

1. D. Martin, *Textbook on International Law*, 7th edition, (United Kingdom: Oxford University Press, 2013), pp. 5-6.

2. I. Brownlie, *Principles of Public International Law*, 8th edition, (London: Oxford University Press, 2012), pp. 30-31.

3. M.N. Shaw, *International Law*, 7th edition, (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2014), pp. 94-96.

4. Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended), Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999, Section 12.

5. M. Akehurst, *A Modern Introduction to International Law*, 7th edition, (London: Routledge, 1997), pp. 51-52.

6. R.N. Nwabueze, “Historical and Comparative Contexts for the Evolution of Conflict of Laws in Nigeria,” *ILSA Journal of International & Comparative Law*, Vol. 8, Article 2, 2002, pp 58-59.

7. R.J. Miller & O. Stitz, “The International Law of Colonialism in East Africa: Germany, England, and The Doctrine of Discovery,” *Duke Journal of Comparative & International Law*, Vol 32:1, 2021, p.53.

of a people in a given community which by common adoption and acquiescence on their part and by long and unvarying habit, has acquired to some extent an element of compulsion, and force of law with regard to the community. Though colonialist imposed English law as the principal legal administration, they recognised the customary laws and incorporated them within the colonial legal system but with a subordinate position to English law. However, to enable the colonialists have a seamless fusion of the legal frameworks, most of the customary laws were termed “barbaric” or “uncivilised” and were either revised to conform to English law or abolished.⁸ The consequence was that there was erosion of some local indigenous regulations as colonial authorities enacted laws that took precedence over the customary practices.

4. Colonial Courts and Customary Law in Nigeria

The Colonial courts were established in major cities and managed by British judges or colonial officers trained in English law. The courts usually regarded customary law in light of principles of English law. As a result, there was selectivity in using customary practices. This selective application was justified on the basis that customary law should not be “repugnant to natural justice, equity and good conscience,” a standard which, in practice reflected English legal standards.⁹ Consequently, most customary practices that did not conform to the principles of English law were either altered or removed.

5. Emergence of Dual Legal System

Among the most salient features that the legal system of Nigeria suffered at the hands of the British colonial administration was the establishment of a dual system of law. This coexistence of British common law and customary law provided that the former shall be applied in the Colonial Courts, while the latter should be in the native courts. This dual structure created a very convoluted legal regime whereby individuals were subjected to different laws depending on the nature of the legal issue and to what jurisdiction they fell.¹⁰ Furthermore, the imposition of British legal principles and the establishment of a dual legal system created a hybrid legal system in Nigeria. The hybrid system had both English law and customary law in coexistence, thereby creating a more complex legal environment.

6. Post-Colonial Legal Reforms and Constitutional Developments in Nigeria

At independence in 1960, Nigeria started making attempts to decolonise the legal system and lay a framework that would reflect the sovereignty of the nation with rich cultural diversities. Most of the structures and legal principles inherited from the period of colonial rule were retained in the 1960 Constitution. This Constitution was thus a compromise document in relations to the delicate balance between maintenance

8. A.A. Adeyeye, “Administrative Convenience or Deliberate Reform? The Impacts of the Colonial Judicial Legacy of the Pre-Colonial Justice System in South-Western Nigeria” LLM Theses at Osgoode Hall Law School of York University, Toronto, 2023, p.139.

9. E.A Taiwo, “Repugnancy clause and its impact on customary law: Comparing the South African and Nigerian positions -Some lessons for Nigeria.” *Journal for Juridical Science*, Vol. 34(1), 2009, p. 95

10. T.O. Elias, *The Nature of African Customary Law*, (Manchester: Manchester University Press, 1956), pp. 47-49.

of the existing legal order and adaptation to the demands of real politick which faced a newly independent nation.¹¹

The 1963 Republican Constitution of Nigeria provided the nation with its first serious strike toward a properly sovereign legal system. In this constitution, headship changed from a British monarch to a Nigerian president. During this era, the substantive content of the law remained the same, as the English common law retained an influential position in courts, which was the primary motive.¹² Notwithstanding, partial achievements were made because legal stability and predictability were possible in the newly independent state as there were no obvious immediate alternatives to the existing English law.

The 1979 Constitution was a sure diversion from the earlier legal frameworks of government, as it ushered in a presidential form of government modelled around that of the United States. This shift according to Nwabueze “was compelled by the necessity for instituting a more stable and coherent political system in the aftermath of the civil war in Nigeria between 1967 and 1970, and under military rule thereafter.”¹³ This was an attempt at a more evenly balanced federal system where the states were to be relatively independent and have a clear separation of powers between the executive, legislative, and judicial arms. It was an ephemeral arrangement because it was suspended following a military coup in 1983. Notwithstanding, Suberu has posited that, “the 1979 Constitution provided foundational work for later constitutional developments, particularly the extant Constitution of 1999.”¹⁴

The Constitution of 1999, otherwise known as the Fourth Republic Constitution, came into being after Nigeria had returned to civilian rule from long years of military dictatorship. Although very similar to the 1979 constitution, new provisions in it strengthened democracy, human rights, and good governance.¹⁵

7. CASE STUDIES IN THE APPLICATION OF INTERNATIONAL LAW IN NIGERIA

7.1 *Abacha v. Fawehinmi (2000) 6 NWLR 16*

The lawsuit started with allegation against General Sani Abacha by Chief Gani Fawehinmi in 1996. Generally speaking, Fawehinmi’s legal appeal focused on Abacha government actions which violated his basic personal liberties and culminated in wrongful incarceration. The main issue before the court was whether, without specific legislative enactments by the National Assembly, international treaties like the ACHPR would be immediately applicable in Nigerian courts. Fawehinmi argued that the terms of the ACHPR should apply in the Nigerian legal system as Nigeria had already ratified it. Conversely, the administration of Abacha argued that international

11. P. Okoli, “Former British Colonies: The Constructive Role of African Courts in the Development of Private International Law.” *University of Bologna Law Review*, vol. 7, no. 2, 2022, pp. 121.

12. J. S. Omotola, “Constitutional Reforms and the Politics of Governance in Nigeria,” *African Journal of Political Science* 15, no. 2 (2007), pp 29-31.

13. F. Nwabueze, *Nigeria’s Republican Constitution: A Critical Review*, (London: Oxford University Press, 1974), pp. 37-39.

14. Suberu, “Nigeria’s Permanent Constitutional Transition: Military Rule, Civilian Instability and ‘True Federalism’ in a Deeply Divided Society,” *Occasional Paper Series*, No. 34, Forum of Federations, 2019, p.4.

15. P. Okafor, “Military Rule and the Crisis of Constitutionalism in Nigeria,” *Journal of African Law*, Vol.40, No. 2 (1996), pp.134-136.

accords needed domestication first before they could acquire legal power within the nation.¹⁶ In its ruling, the Nigerian Supreme Court created a clear line in the sand by separating international law from its application vis-à-vis the validity of such legislation within the Nigerian legal scene. Nevertheless, the court came to see that the African Charter (Ratification and Enforcement) Act had been adopted into Nigerian legislation and that Fawehinmi may rely on its clauses to contest infringement of human rights.¹⁷ This ruling set a significant precedent for any situation in which international human rights obligations might be a concern as it offered a way to incorporate international legal norms into Nigerian law.

7.2 *Mojekwu v. Ejikeme (2005) 5 NWLR 19*

The Nigerian Court of Appeal addressed gender discrimination in traditional inheritance procedures in the historic case of *Mojekwu v. Ejikeme*.¹⁸ In this instance, the appellant, Mojekwu, sought to inherit family property under the customary *oli-ekpe*, a patriarchal Igbo custom which allows only male successors. The appellant, Mojekwu, contended that the custom breached the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW), which Nigeria had ratified but not domesticated. Led by Justice Niki Tobi, the Court of Appeal deemed the *oli-ekpe* tradition repugnant to good conscience, fairness, and natural justice. Although CEDAW is not directly domesticated in Nigeria, the allusion to it showed how international law could affect court decisions in human rights matters where customary law runs counter to universal human rights standards.

7.3 *SERAP v. Federal Republic of Nigeria (ECW/CCJ/APP/08/09 20*

In this case, the Socio-Economic Rights and Accountability Project (SERAP) filed a complaint against the Federal Republic of Nigeria for violating the rights of education and protection of children especially those within the Niger Delta region against exploitation under both the ACHPR and the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR). SERAP, therefore, asked for a declaration of Nigeria's failure in fulfilling its responsibility in accordance with international law and accordingly requested specific remedial measures.¹⁹ In this case, the ECOWAS Community Court of Justice (CCJ) placed particular emphasis on Nigeria's obligations under the ACHPR and other international covenants. The ECOWAS Court, in the judgment, indicated that the Nigerian government's denial of basic education to its people, especially in the poorer areas of the Niger Delta, had run contrary to Articles 17 and 18 of the ACHPR, which provide for the right to education and protection of the family and vulnerable groups. The application of these international provisions revealed the acceptance of international law as a means to advance accountability for violations of socio-economic rights. The judgment also encouraged greater recourse to international tribunals for enforcing human rights protections in situations where

16. Abacha v. Fawehinmi (2000)6 NWLR ...

17. African Charter (Ratification and Enforcement) Act, Cap A9, Laws of the Federation of Nigeria (1990).

18. Mojekwu v. Ejikeme (2000) 5 NWLR (Pt. 657) 402

19. SERAP v. Federal Republic of Nigeria (ECW/CCJ/APP/08/09).

domestic remedies are either unavailable or ineffective. Little wonder that at the breakdown of law and order/or threats, attention is directed at the international scene for succour.²⁰

7.4 *Attorney-General of the Federation v. Attorney-General of Abia State & 35 Ors* 22

This case was a dispute between the federal government and several oil-producing states over what is meant by Section 162(2) of the 1999 Constitution that prescribed the allocation of not less than 13% of the revenue derived from natural resources to the area of derivation.²¹ In this case, the court reiterated that whereas Nigeria may have signed some international conventions on the exploitation of natural resources, the legal framework relating to revenue allocation must be guided by domestic law unless those treaties are properly incorporated into Nigerian law. The court maintained that the constitution of Nigeria remains the supreme law, and international law can only influence judicial interpretation when it aligns with or has been domestically enacted. In this case, international law could not be applied in the court unless domestic legislation has been enacted, entrenching domestic law at the heart of resource allocation. The decision in this case explained the attitude of the judiciary in upholding the supremacy of the constitution of Nigeria while appreciating the relevance of international law.

7.5 *Registered Trustees of the Constitutional Rights Project (CRP) v. Nigeria* 23

The military regimes in Nigeria especially under General Sani Abacha, were notorious for affront on human rights in the country. This period was characterised by a strong contention for human rights and the rule of law. Notwithstanding the oppressive atmosphere, the Constitutional Rights Project (CRP), a Nigerian human rights group, opposes the government's blatant disregard for basic freedom.²² The case amongst others held that Nigeria, being a state party to the ACHPR, was obliged to respect, protect, and fulfil the rights enunciated therein. The African Commission further held that Nigeria had violated the Charter, particularly in respect of the rights to a fair trial and the right to life. Although the decision of the African Commission is not binding, it had a great moral and persuasive weight upon which Nigeria based its subsequent approach to the protection of human rights.²³

20. For instance, in the Edo State gubernatorial elections of September 21, 2020, when it became obvious that the All Progressives Congress (APC) could use federal might to rig the elections, most PDP stalwarts clamoured for international observers' presence. See Edo Decides, ITV Benin Programme, 18th September 2024.

21. *Attorney-General of the Federation v. Attorney-General of Abia State & 35 Ors* (2002) 6 NWLR (Pt. 764) 542

22. *Registered Trustees of the Constitutional Rights Project (CRP) v. Nigeria*, Africa Commission on Human and Peoples' Rights, Communication No. 102/93, 1998.

23. Federal Ministry of Justice, "Nigeria's 6th Periodic Country Report: - 2015- 2016 on The Implementation of the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights in Nigeria," Abuja, 2017

8. CHALLENGES AND PROSPECT OF INTERNATIONAL LAW COMPLIANCE IN NIGERIA JUDICIAL SYSTEM

There is no denying the fact that international law adherence has been so problematic in Nigeria. Domestication of treaties are cumbersome and sometimes erratic process in Nigeria. Central to this factor is the doctrinal debate that has arisen concerning dualism and monism in Nigeria's approach to international law.

8.1 *Dualism*

Dualism is a legal doctrine which posits that international law and domestic law are two separate legal systems, operating independently of each other. The Nigeria model is a clear example of the way things are done as its Constitution and the legislative process requires that international treaties need to be domesticated before they can operate legally in the appellate courts. The dualist approach seemed to have created several problems in Nigeria.

8.2 *Monism*

Unlike dualism, monism perceives the international and municipal legal systems as one; thus, norms of international law are domestically applied as part of the body of laws on its own, without additional legislation. Although the monist approach is theoretically preferable to achieve instantaneous enforcement of international commitments, it suffered from practical stumbling blocks in Nigeria. The dualistic structure somehow put in place took away the full application of international law in Nigerian practice. In fact, Nigerian courts and learned scholars in Nigeria, while appreciating the superiority of the monist doctrine, "the present legal regime urges the translation of international agreements into local legislation through the legislating process".²⁴

"Generally speaking, by virtue of section 12 of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, Nigeria is a dualist State. The legal implication of this is that before any international law source such as a treaty or convention can become binding in Nigeria, it must first of all be legislatively domesticated by the National Assembly. The only exception to the foregoing rule is in relation to labour treaties. Thus, section 254(C) of the 2010 Third Alteration Act to the 1999 Constitution provides that all labour-related treaties shall be automatically applicable in Nigeria without any need for domestication. It could thus be argued that the Third Alteration Act introduced a monist dimension into the largely dualist system in Nigeria."²⁵

The aforesaid notwithstanding, there are also practical implementation challenges and enforcement issues. Even after the signing and domestication of treaties through ratification, the application and practice of these set of norms still proved very dicey. Also, lack of political will have been a bane in the application of international law in Nigeria. Political leadership and policy-makers are often reluctant to implement and apply the norms and standards set out in international law. Their interests in domestic matters could have overridden those in international relations, and as a consequence,

24. E.O. Okebukola, "The Application of International Law in Nigeria and the Façade of Dualism," *Nnamdi Azikiwe University Journal of International Law and Jurisprudence*, 2020, pp. 15–28.

25. Oral interview with Dr Philip Oamen, Associate Course Director of the Master of Laws Programme at Birmingham City University, United Kingdom, 22/8/2024.

not ready to implement fully or enforce the internationally binding treaties.²⁶ Additionally, there have been institutional weaknesses in the application and enforcement of international law in Nigeria. These are exacerbated by the absence of coordination at various levels of government. Again, while the federal government may ratify international treaties, the state and local authorities often fail to have mechanisms in place for enforcing such standards uniformly. Fragmentation can thus lead to serious protection and accountability gaps.²⁷ Inadequate training in international legal standards and absence of special training courses and continuing education on international legal norms has been identified as militating problems in the Nigerian judiciary. Judicial officers who were not in a position to acquire proper and well-rounded knowledge and understanding of international law, have evidently rubbished the application of these norms when approaching domestic cases. Traditionally, for example, the legal education system required emphasis on domestic law and less importance on international legal principles. As a result, the judges could not effectively integrate the set of international standards of human rights in their rulings, hence “rendering their overall adherence to international law compromised.”²⁸ Added to the myriads of obstacles, general political opposition, and bureaucratic delays, the processes of bringing national laws into conformity with international standards often lacked the broad consensus these changes actually required. This shortcoming according to Wermuth “is a key reflection of wider problems in Nigeria’s political and legal system, where vested interests and political instability often stand in the way.”²⁹

9. Recommendation

Having considered the aforesaid, the question of the way forward for the Nigerian judiciary comes to mind. This study proposes the undermentioned:

1. Introduction to legal reforms and updating domestic laws would eventually bring national laws in line with international commitments. The scope of legislative reform should focus on the direct translation of international treaties into national laws without engaging in excessive and often red-tape legislative procedures. This would involve “an Act to amend the Treaty Ratification and Enforcement Act by ensuring smooth procedures in domesticating international agreements.”³⁰
2. Judicial training should be emphasised. This implies that broad international law courses, both theoretical and practical should be introduced in the Nigerian judicial training curriculum, including training collaboration with international legal bodies and institutions that “would equip and enable them to apply such

26. Human Rights Watch, World Report: Nigeria, September 2008.

27. C.E. Okeke & M.I. Anushiem, “Implementation of Treaties in Nigeria: Issues, Challenges and the Way Forward.” *Nigerian Journal of International Law and Jurisprudence*, vol. 10, No. 1, 2020, p. 218.

28. M. Shreekrishna, “The Nepali Perspective on Judicial Education: A Brief Review,” *Judicial Education and Training, Journal of International Education for Judicial Training*, Iss. 4, 2015, p.57.

29. C. Trenkov-Wermuth, *United Nations justice: Legal and judicial reform in governance operations*, (Tokyo: United Nations University Press, 2010), p.18.

30. C.U. Akpkwe, A.O. Adeniyi, & S.S Bakare, “The Impact of Judicial Reforms on Legal Systems: A Review in African Countries.” *International Journal of Applied Research in Social Sciences*, Vol. 6, Iss.3, March 2024, p.206.

international law when called upon.”³¹ Additionally, regular continuous legal education programs should be undertaken with the international legal profession in rapidly changing international legal standards.

3. Mechanisms for law enforcement should be strengthened in order to ensure that the standards are implemented and upheld duly.
4. Attention should be devoted to structural issues. The reforms should be targeted at enhancing the independence of the judiciary, reducing corruption, and increasing efficiency. Structural reforms that build better capacity and integrity within the judiciary would go a long way toward “creating an enabling environment in which international law can be applied.”³²
5. Enhanced collaboration and technical support to the judiciary would profit Nigeria judiciary a great deal. This could include community outreach programs, public education campaigns, and joint projects for enhancing legal literacy and creating a culture of respect for human rights. This may, however, “be complemented through technical assistance provided by international organizations.”³³
6. Awareness creation on international law issues is a yardstick in embedding the culture of compliance for both the legal and political systems in Nigeria.³⁴ It can also emphasise the need for compliance with international standards and garner public support for legal reforms.
7. Leveraging capacity building with international organisations have assisted Nigeria in a number of ways on a variety of projects, each aimed at bringing the nation into full adherence with the tenets of international law. This has taken the form of technical assistance, training workshops, and assistance in the drafting of anti-corruption frameworks.³⁵

In conclusion, it could be seen that compliance with international law in the Nigerian judiciary is a many-faceted challenge that entail both doctrinal and practical hurdles. While there are, without a doubt, huge challenges to successful implementation, there are equally opportunities for improvement through legal reforms, an increase in institutional capacity, and more collaboration. Overcoming these challenges requires concerted and exceptional efforts from all actors toward reorientation in Nigeria’s domestic legal system with international legal standards and for the realisation of human rights and the rule of law.

31. I. Archi, “Judicial Training and The Rule of Law” in A. Camri (Eds), *Judicial Education and Training*, Journal of the International Organization for Judicial Training, Vol. 1, 2013, p.19

32. N. Rendak and D. Eastman, “Legal and Judicial Reform: Recent Developments and Prospects” in S. Ishikawa and K. Nakamura (Eds), *Cambodia: Rebuilding for a Challenging Future*, (International Monetary Fund, 2006), p.106.

33. Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights (OHCHR, “Engagement and Partnerships with Civil Society,” *Manual on Human Rights Monitoring*, United Nations, 2011, p.5.

34. United Nations Human Rights Council, *Annual Report of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights and Reports of the Office of the High Commissioner and the Secretary-General*, 24 Feb.–20 Mar. 2020, A/HRC/43/26, p.8.

35. United Nations on Drugs and Crime, *strengthening Judicial Integrity and Capacity in Nigeria*, Progress Report, 2003, pp.3–6